

Synthesis of α -Amino adipic Acid

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A two-step synthesis of α -amino adipic acid in quite encouraging yield through reduction and hydrolysis of azlactone of succinic anhydride with hydriodic acid in presence of red phosphorus has been reported.

SEVERAL synthetic schemes for the preparation of α -amino adipic acid have been reviewed by Greenstein and Winitz¹. Published methods show that only the azlactones of acetic and phthalic anhydrides have been used for the synthesis of amino acids. Attenburrow and co-workers² prepared threonine from 2-phenyl-4-(1-hydroxyethylidene)-5-oxazolone, an azlactone of acetic anhydride. Recently³, we have employed 2-phenyl-4-phthalidene-5-oxazolone for the synthesis of β -amino- β -(*o*-benzene carboxylic acid) alanine. We now describe the formation of 2-phenyl-4-succinylidene-5-oxazolone and α -amino adipic acid from this azlactone.

Unlike the analogous preparation of azlactones of carbonyl compounds, reaction of succinic anhydride (1) with hippuric acid (2) gives some other products in addition to the azlactone. Treatment of the anhydride (1) with hippuric acid (2) in presence of fused sodium acetate as a base catalyst and acetic anhydride affords 2-phenyl-4-succinylidene-5-oxazolone (3) as well as benzoic acid (4) and N-acetylglycine (5). This is due to the transformation of hippuric acid into benzoic acid and glycine to some extent by water produced during the course of azlactone formation in the reaction mixture. The liberated glycine reacts with acetic anhydride to yield N-acetylglycine (5). If in this reaction, the sodium acetate is replaced by triethylamine, the rate of hydrolysis is increased and the compounds (4) and (5) are formed in excess.

Condensation of glycine with equimolecular proportion of succinic anhydride in presence of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate results in the formation N-acetylglycine (5) and water soluble pigments, when the mixture is warmed for various lengths of time. The compound (5) does not react with succinic anhydride to give 2-methyl-4-succinylidene-5-oxazolone, an analogue of the product (3). If excess of glycine is taken keeping other reaction conditions the same, polymerization takes place and a green fluorescing polymer is obtained.

Subjection of the compound (3) to hydrolysis with hydriodic acid in presence of red phosphorus and glacial acetic acid leads to simultaneous scission of the lactone and oxazolone rings as well as the benzoyl group. The carbon-carbon double bond is also reduced during the hydrolysis. No difficulty is encountered in the isolation of the amino acid (6) from the reaction mixture. After hydrolysis is complete, which takes 2 hr, the contents are filtered and the filtrate is evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure after trituration with solvent ether. In this way the salt of α -amino adipic acid is obtained which on treatment with ammonia gives the free amino acid (6) in a well crystallized form (Fig. 1).

Experimental

Synthesis of 2-phenyl-4-succinylidene-5-oxazolone (3): An intimate mixture of succinic anhydride (10-g), hippuric acid (17.9 g) and fused sodium acetate (8.4 g) was heated with acetic anhydride (30 ml) on an electric hot plate to obtain a clear solution and then on a steam bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water. The gummy product separated was extracted with sodium carbonate solution to remove benzoic acid and then with light petroleum ether (40-60°). The azlactone was obtained on evaporation of the ether. This was purified by a column of alumina using benzene; m.p. 114-15°, yield 4.19 g (16%). Anal. Found: C, 64.49; H, 3.70; N, 5.48. Calcd. for C₁₅H₉NO₄; C, 64.20; H, 3.73; N, 5.76%.

The water layer obtained from the above reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in methanol. On cooling, crystallized product, N-acetylglycine (5), was obtained. This was filtered and dried, m.p. 205-6°, mixed m.p. 205°. Anal. Found: C, 40.79; H, 6.31; N, 12.23. Calcd. for C₄H₇NO₂; C, 41.02; H, 6.03; N, 11.96%.

Synthesis of α -amino adipic acid (6): 2-Phenyl-4-succinylidene-5-oxazolone (2 g) was refluxed with

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Fig. 1

a mixture of hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7; 15 ml), glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and red phosphorus (2.5 g) for 2 hr. Unreacted phosphorus was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness under diminished pressure. The residue was taken up in 20 ml of water and re-evaporated. The residue was again suspended in water (25 ml) and extracted several times with ether to remove benzoic acid. The aqueous layer was neutralized carefully with ammonia solution. The separated amino acid (6) was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried; m.p. 204-5° (lit.^{4,5} m.p. 206° and 202°), yield 0.88 g (95%). IR(KBr) 3020, 1900, 1650, 1580, 1500, 1250, 1180 and 760 cm^{-1} . Anal. Found: C, 44.52; H, 7.08; N, 8.91. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4$; C, 44.71; H, 6.88; N, 8.69%.

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